

STUDY ON INTERFACES AND PROPERTIES OF ALUMINUM
ALLOY COMPOSITE REINFORCED WITH METAL FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

The longitudinal tensile and fatigue properties of the Al-Sn-Cu-Ni composite reinforced with metal fibres have been studied. The fracture surfaces and structures of the interface have also been investigated with the help of SEM, EPMA, X-ray Diffraction. Experiments for inquiring into the formation mechanism of the interface were conducted. The results show that the interfacial layer constituted of FeAl_3 and Fe_2Al_5 is beneficial to strengthening the composite. The tensile, fatigue fracture surfaces show that their fracture mechanism is different.

KEYWORDS: Interface; Fracture; Diffusion; Solidification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many countries have been researching on metal matrix composites reinforced with carbon, silicon carbides, boron fibres. Some extremely effective results have been gained. When high toughness and strength are demanded, metal fibre possesses its own characteristics although metal fibre isn't lighter than other fibres such as carbon fibre and SiC fibre, etc. In some papers [1], aluminum alloy composites reinforced with steel fibres, stainless steel fibres have been studied. It is pointed out in reference [2] that metal fibre possesses a higher density than carbon and silicon carbon fibres, but its wettability with matrix is better. Also, the metal fibre and the matrix will react with each other to form a layer or multiple layers around the fibre. The reports on the properties of aluminum alloy composite reinforced with metal fibres, the formation mechanism of the interface and its effect on properties have rarely been studied. The main purpose of this paper is to investigate them.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The composition of the aluminum alloy matrix used is 6.5%Sn, 1.0%Cu, 1.0%Ni. The electric conductivity of the matrix is 47% of the copper's. The metal fibres used are zinc-coated iron wires the diameters of which are 0.35mm and 0.5mm. The surfaces of the fibres are only rinsed by acetone to eliminate the greasy dirt.

The tensile samples are fabricated by using the continuous casting experimental machine, as shown in Fig.1. The fatigue samples are fabricated by using the permanent mold casting, as shown in Fig.2.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The longitudinal tensile strength and interface of the iron wire / Al-Sn-Cu-Ni composite.

Fig.3 shows the longitudinal tensile strength of the composites containing different V_f . The theory tensile strength of the composite ($V_f=2.5\%$) σ_c is 114.8N/mm^2 (According to the mixture rule of composite). Thus the practically measured value of σ_c is higher by 35.2N/mm^2 than the theoretical value of σ_c . We take it as the result of the formation of the interfacial layer around the metal fibre (Fig.4). The interfacial layer acts as a high strength thin-wall-tube to reinforce the metal fibre.

The interfacial layer is sub-divided into two parts as shown in Fig.4. The one near the metal fibre is columnar grain structure called inner interfacial layer, the other near the matrix is called outer interfacial layer constituted of aluminum and some reaction products in the form of particles and blocks composed of fine grains. Quantitative EPMA (as shown in Fig.5) on interface in Fig.4 was conducted to show that the inner interfacial layer structure is Fe_2Al_5 (45%Fe, 52%Al, 0.7%Zn), the outer interfacial layer structure is $\text{Al}+\text{FeAl}_3$. (The composition of FeAl_3 is 31%Fe, 51%Al, 17%Sn, 0.74%Zn). The intermetallic compound in outer layer should precisely be FeAl_3 solid solution containing Sn and Zn. It is also proved by X-ray Diffraction that the interfacial intermetallic compounds are FeAl_3 and Fe_2Al_5 with approximately orthorhombic structure. The X-ray diffraction result is illustrated in Fig.6.

When the aluminum alloy melt contacts the metal fibre, the fibre surface zone is sharply heated to form an activated state, the Zn-coated layer and its transient layer on the fibre will quickly dissolve into the matrix melt. Simultaneously, the Fe, Al and other alloy elements mutually diffuse to react at the interface, the mutual diffusion layer is formed. When continuous casting and permanent mold casting are used to fabricate composites, the quickly formed liquid aluminum alloy layer containing Fe will rapidly solidify to form the outer interfacial layer. FeAl_3 compound (In Fe-Al system, FeAl_3 compound contains a small quantity of Al atoms) is first formed in pace with the Fe element content increase in the aluminum alloy matrix right near the metal fibre. As the diffusion continues, FeAl_3 layer is increased in thickness, the Fe-rich alu-

minum alloy layer will be also increased in thickness. Fe_2Al_5 will be nucleated in FeAl_3 when the Fe content in FeAl_3 increases. Fe_2Al_5 will preferentially grow into iron fibre according to diffusion flux direction. So the Fe_2Al_5 columnar will be very directional, its C-axis which aluminum rapidly diffuses along should be the diffusion flux direction. The original interface will move into metal fibre as the result of the growth of Fe_2Al_5 . In Fe-rich Al-Fe layer, the Fe atoms will also diffuse into the matrix through a longer distance from the interface, and the Al-Fe alloy layer will be reduced in thickness. The reaction between metal fibre and matrix melt is shown in Fig.7.

The reaction between the metal fibre and the matrix melt is extremely rapid as a result of the fast cooling effect of the continuous casting, permanent mold casting and the chilling effect of the fibres. So the rapidly formed Al-Fe alloy layer will be undercooled to a large extent. The undercooling of Al-Fe layer will also be relatively increased when the Fe content increases in Al-Fe layer according to the Fe-Al system equilibrium diagram. There're larger quantity of atom clusters in Al-Fe layer at the liquidus [3] the clusters will be the nucleation centers of FeAl_3 . When the Al-Fe layer solidifies, FeAl_3 will be voluminously formed in the form of particles and blocks constituted of FeAl_3 intermetallic compound aggregations. The morphology of the outer interfacial layer is illustrated in Fig.8.

3.2 The fatigue strength of the iron wire / Al-Sn-Cu-Ni composite

3.2.1 The effect of the pouring temperature on the fatigue strength.

When liquid infiltration method is used to fabricate the composite, the pouring temperature has strong effect on the composite properties. There are two reasons for that: One is that the variation of the pouring temperature will result in the variation of the thickness of the interfacial layer and the variation of the interfacial layer properties. The other is that the metal fibre will be somewhat damaged at the high temperature. It can be seen from Fig.9 that the sample poured at 830°C possesses a better fatigue property than that poured at 800°C . The reason for that is that the interfacial layer of the sample poured at 830°C has a proper thickness ($15\text{--}25\mu\text{m}$) and a better interfacial bonding. It can be seen (from Fig.10) that the fatigue crack on the right side propagating from matrix to the interfacial layer continues propagating into fibre across the interfacial layer as the result of the stronger bonding strength at the interface. When it propagates to the interfacial layer, the interfacial layer begins to spall as a result of the weaker bonding, so the crack propagates along the interfacial layer. When a stronger bonding is faced, the crack turns to propagate into the matrix.

3.2.2 The effect of the iron fibre diameter on the fatigue property.

It can be seen from Fig.10 that the fatigue failure cycle number of the composite containing 0.5mm diameter fibres is higher than that of the composite containing 0.35mm diameter fibres at the same stress. This result reveals that the composite containing thick fibres has a better fatigue property than containing thin fibres. The above results coincide with S.J.Harris' result [4].

3.2.3 The analysis of the Fracture surface.

Fig.13 is the SEM fractograph of the tensile fracture surface. It is noticed that both the matrix

and the iron fibres rupture in the form of ductile fracture. FeAl_3 compounds in interfacial layer can be seen on the interfacial layer fracture surfaces. The interfacial layer cracks and spalls from the fibre when the iron fibre necks at high stress. Some brittle Fe_2Al_5 columnar grains can be detected on the wall of the necking iron fibre. The brittle fracture of Fe_2Al_5 is very similar to the sliding bands on iron fibre. So it is known that the bonding of Fe_2Al_5 with the iron fibre is stronger enough. The gap between the matrix and the interfacial layer is considered to be created by the ductile deformation of the matrix and the aluminum in the outer interfacial layer. Fig.13 illustrates the tensile fracture model.

It can be noticed from Fig.14 that the fracture surface is very flat. Either the iron fibre or the interfacial layer or the matrix has a cleavage fracture surface with a fishbone-like morphology and quasi-cleavage fracture surface with a stream-like morphology and tearing ridges. The running directions of the tearing ridges mostly point to the iron fibre. It indicates that iron fibres play a better reinforcing role in the fatigue fracture of the composite. The propagation of the fatigue crack is restricted by the fibres and the interfacial layers. When the fatigue limit is reached, the fatigue cracks will be linked together. The tearing ridges formed point to the iron fibres, and the iron fibres will fail in the form of low stress fatigue fracture. Fig.16 illustrates the low stress fatigue fracture model of the composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 4.1 The interfacial layer formed in iron wire / Al-Sn-Cu-Ni composite fabricated by the continuous casting and the permanent mold casting method can be sub-divided into two parts: the inner interfacial layer which is a diffusion layer constituted of Fe_2Al_5 columnar grains, the outer interfacial layer which is a solidification layer constituted of aluminum and FeAl_3 fine grains. The interfacial layer is beneficial to strengthening the composite. The measured tensile strength of the composite is higher by 35.2N/mm^2 ($V_f = 2.5\%$) than the value theoretically calculated.
- 4.2 Both the pouring temperature of the matrix and the iron fibre diameter have stronger effects on the fatigue property of the composite. In this paper, pouring temperature at 830°C is better than that at 800°C , 0.5mm diameter is better than 0.35mm diameter.
- 4.3 Fatigue tensile fracture surfaces show that their fracture mechanism is different.

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Fig.1 Sketch drawing of the continous casting experimental machine

Fig.2 Sketch of the permanent mold casting device.

Fig.3 Variation of composite strength with fibre volume fraction

Fig.5 EPMA quantitative elements analysis results across the interface in iron fibre / Al-Sn-Cu-Ni composite, (a)Al, (b)Fe, (c)Zn, (d)Sn.

Fig.4 Typical microstructure of interface

Fig.8 A model for the outer interfacial layer.

Fig.6 X-ray diffraction pattern of iron fibre / Al-Sn-Cu-Ni composite.

Fig.7 A model for the reaction between the liquid aluminum alloy matrix and the iron fibre

Fig.9 Effect of pouring temperature on stress-fatigue cycle number curve

Fig.10 Scanning electron micrograph of propagation of fatigue crack

Fig.14 Scanning electron micrograph of fatigue fracture surface

Fig.11 Effect of iron fibre diameter on stress-fatigue cycle number curve

Fig.12 Scanning electron micrograph of tensile fracture surface

Fig.13 Schematic illustration of tensile fracture mode

Fig.15 Schematic illustration of fatigue fracture mode in Low Stress Fatigue

